

Manufacturing Information System in the Coca-Cola Company

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Abstract

The Manufacturing Information System (Manufacturing Information System) provides information to all company managers relating to the company's manufacturing operations. The four output subsystems, namely production, inventory, quality, and costs, provide reports on subjects of great importance in manufacturing. In manufacturing information systems, computers are not only used to run the system itself. However, a computer can be a special device for producing goods, such as how robots can be used to produce goods more effectively and efficiently. Manufacturing information systems also use computers both conceptually and as an element within the company. The four output subsystems, namely production, inventory, quality, and costs, provide reports on subjects of great importance in manufacturing. In manufacturing information systems, computers are not only used to run the system itself. However, a computer can be a special device for producing goods, such as how robots can be used to produce goods more effectively and efficiently. Manufacturing information systems also use computers both conceptually and as an element in the physical production system. The purpose of writing this paper is to analyze and evaluate the use of the Manufacturing Information System at The Coca-Cola Company and how Coca Cola can improve performance through its Manufacturing Information System

Keywords: Manufacturing Information Systems, Performance, Coca Cola Company

Introduction

Management information system is a computer-based system that makes information available to users who have similar needs. SIM users usually consist of formal corporate organizational entities or subsidiary sub-units. The information provided by SIM explains the company or one of its main systems in terms of what has happened in the past, what is happening, and what is likely to happen in the future. Information systems are always changing. The information systems used today are increasingly advanced and very broad in scope. The level of society's need for information is the beginning of information system development. Updated and accurate information makes the company develop better. A good information system can be an advantage that a company has so that it can survive in the long term.

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Information Systems

An information system is the process of collecting, processing, analyzing and disseminating information for certain purposes (Cegielski, 2014:6). According to Leitch (2011:93), an information system is a system within an organization that meets the needs of managing daily transactions, supporting operations, managerial and strategic activities of an organization and providing certain external parties with the required reports. Information system is any organized combination of people, hardware, software, or databases that collects, changes, and disseminates information within an organizational form O'brien (2011:62).

Figure 8.9 A Model of a Manufacturing Information System

Source: Raymond McLeod & George P. Schell, 2016

According to Rahman & Saudin (2022), a manufacturing information system is a computer-based system that works in conjunction with other functional information systems to support company management in solving problems related to manufacturing company products which basically still relies on input, process and output.

Manufacturing Information System Model

⇒ Input Subsystem

- Transaction Processing Subsystem

An accounting information system (AIS) is a transaction processing subsystem used to collect internal data that can explain manufacturing operations related to company and supplier transaction data.

- Industrial Engineering Subsystem

The industrial engineering subsystem is a system that is specially trained to learn about operations in manufacturing and create repair mechanisms. This industrial engineering includes special data within the company for the need to determine production process times.

- Manufacturing Intelligence Subsystem

The manufacturing intelligence subsystem is used to find out the latest developments regarding material sources, workers and machines. The following are several components of the intelligence subsystem:

- Employee information
- Formal system
- Informal system
- Collection of environmental data
- Data testing
- Data maintenance
- Data security
- Retrieval of data in the form of a report

⇒ Output Subsystem

- Production Subsystem

This is every matter related to the process in each part of the department which is tasked with measuring the production of goods.

- Inventory Subsystem

In the inventory subsystem, it provides data related to the number of stock items, holding costs, and safety stock based on the results of input data processing. The function of this inventory system is to be able to measure the volume of production activities starting from processing raw materials until they become materials ready for production.

- Quality Subsystem

The quality subsystem includes time costs, quality, supplier selection, and work performance. The function of the quality system itself is used to measure the quality of the material when it is changed.

- Cost Subsystem

The cost subsystem is used to obtain costs incurred during the production process. The cost system is grouped into two parts, namely purchase costs and maintenance costs.

Discussion

Company profile

Company Name: The Coca-Cola Company

Company Address: 1 Coca Cola Plz NW, Atlanta, Georgia, 30313

Year Founded: 1886

Application: +one by The Coca-Cola Company®

E-mail: press@coca-cola.com / info@coca-cola.co.id

Website: www.coca-colacompany.com / www.coca-cola.com/id/id

Telephone: 1-888-348-2404 / 0800 100 2653
Instagram: thecocacolaco / cocacola_id

Company History

The product that has provided the most famous taste in the world was born in Atlanta, Georgia, on May 8, 1886. Dr. John Stith Pemberton, a local pharmacist, produced syrup for Coca-Cola, and brought a bottle of the new drink. The product down the street to Jacobs Pharmacy, where it was sampled, pronounced "excellent" and sold for five cents a glass as a fountain soda. Carbonated water was combined with the new syrup to produce a drink that was at once "Delicious and Refreshing," a theme that continues to resonate today wherever Coca-Cola is enjoyed.

Vision

Creating brands and drink choices that people love and enjoy, to refresh their body and soul. And done in ways that create more sustainable businesses and a better shared future that makes a difference in people's lives, communities and our planet.

Objective

To Refresh the world. Make a difference.

Analysis and Evaluation of Manufacturing Information Systems: The Coca-Cola Company

⇒ Input Subsystem

• Transaction Processing Subsystem

Transaction Processing System (TPS) in which The Coca-Cola Company's activities are divided into individual transaction processes and processes, namely:

- Drink and syrup solvent industry
- Distribution of concentrates to local and foreign bottling companies
- Production of soft drinks by mixing solvents with carbonated water via bottle and can operations
- Finished product packaging
- Distribution to wholesalers and retailers

As a multinational company, The Coca-Cola Company uses high-speed computers connected via the internet for communications in international offices. This makes communication easy, fast and cheap, allowing companies to make decisions quickly. The company maintains a computerized database of customers, suppliers and bottling and canning operations. More than $\frac{3}{4}$ of its annual marketing spend is IT-oriented to provide mobile connections to customers, social networking sites and loyalty programs.

Evaluation: The Coca-Cola Company's Transaction Processing System is a significant asset that not only facilitates day-to-day operations but also supports the company's strategic decisions. In evaluating the Coca-Cola Company Transaction Processing Subsystem, it can be concluded that the company has succeeded in implementing a strong system to support its complex operations. TPS plays a key role in facilitating the transaction process from start to finish, covering the beverage solvent and syrup industry,

concentrate distribution, soft drink production, finished product packaging, and distribution to wholesalers and retailers.

- Industrial Engineering Subsystem

Industrial engineering subsystems include systems in industry in groups of expertise that apply industrial engineering approaches to design, evaluate and increase productivity in an integrated system of people, materials, equipment, energy, technology, information.

- Production Management as a Development in Industrial Engineering

In industrial engineering, the role of production management is one of the keys to industrial development at the Coca-Cola Company, and innovation is one of the keys to success that makes the Coca-Cola Company bigger, more widely known, and contributes to the Indonesian people and nation. Through research and development (Research & Development), Coca-Cola continues to innovate to create new products, packaging, marketing strategies, equipment, sales that are quality, creative, and have their own characteristics by understanding consumer needs and behavior, as well as the potential of natural resources. Indonesia, Coca-Cola innovates by creating new products that make Coca-Cola fast food drink products have a variety of flavors and choices.

The Coca-Cola system recently launched its newest production line in Indonesia called the Affordable Small Sparkling Package (ASSP) bottle. Technology development in collaboration with KHS GmbH, Germany, allows Coca-Cola to produce high quality and lighter plastic bottles, which are the first of their kind in Indonesia. This technology reduces plastic use by more than 40% or more than 800 tons per year in Indonesia. ASSP technology is one way Coca-Cola contributes to the challenge of managing plastic waste without compromising product integrity and safety.

- Cost Control as Coca-Cola Company Cost Control

To obtain reliable and verifiable financial data, the most frequently used secondary data source is the annual report on the official website of the Coca-Cola Company. The data shows the financial position and business operations strategy of the Coca-Cola Company from 2015 to 2017. The main financial data analysis tools used in this paper are horizontal analysis and ratio analysis. Horizontal analysis is used to compare historical data over several accounting periods which presents changes in the number of related financial statement accounts over a certain period of time, which is useful for determining the changing trend of the Coca-Cola Company from 2015 to the Trend of changes in the Coca-Cola Company's financial position in 2017 and the future. front.

Profitability ratios are an important tool for evaluating the profitability of the Coca-Cola Company throughout 2015 to 2017. Profitability ratios involve the gross profit ratio and operating profit ratio which measure and evaluate the Coca-Cola Company's ability to generate profits relative to revenue, which is more meaningful than just comparing income or profits generated by the

Coca-Cola Company, because it shows how well the Coca-Cola Company utilizes its assets to generate profits by taking into account the cost of goods sold and other costs.

Evaluation: The Coca-Cola Company's Industrial Engineering Systems provide a solid foundation for growth and sustainability. The combination of effective production management, continuous innovation and environmental responsibility positions the company as a leader in the beverage industry. Continuous evaluation is required to ensure that these systems remain responsive to market and technological changes.

- Manufacturing Intelligence Subsystem

The manufacturing intelligence subsystem is a small system in the manufacturing information system that can be used to find out information related to the latest developments regarding various material sources such as worker information, formal systems and informal systems. This subsystem is designed to collect and process data related to the latest developments in manufacturing activities. These subsystems provide valuable insights for monitoring and improving operational efficiency and responding to changes in the manufacturing environment. The following are several applications of the manufacturing intelligence subsystem in The Coca-Cola Company:

- Proficiency Software

Coca-Cola uses Proficiency software to increase production at 70 of their manufacturing facilities. The main focus of the renovation was to reduce supply chain complexity, prevent inefficient customization, and perform root cause analysis of problems. By updating the Line Information System (LIS) servers at each facility using Proficiency Historian, iFIX HMI SCADA, and dashboard software, they can deliver real-time and historical data, as well as send Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to the company database via Sync Agent and Microsoft Azure.

These improvements help track production line assets, increase efficiency, reduce equipment losses, and reduce machine downtime. LIS can produce tactical reviews in response to specific operational events and strategic reviews by identifying trends, patterns and root causes. Views on LIS-based systems include plant overview, production line layout, machine status history, short interval control reports, enterprise-level views, etc., accessible via PC, tablet and smartphone. These enhancements provide Coca-Cola with new insights to optimize production by leveraging cloud-based data collection, analysis and protection. They also apply digital guidance to understand problems and make informed decisions.

- Artificial Intelligence:

Coca-Cola extensively utilizes Artificial Intelligence (AI) in its marketing to collect and analyze large volumes of data about its various brands and products offered. In its sales engine, Coca-Cola applies big data analysis and

AI algorithms to interact with its customers. On social media, Coca-Cola uses AI algorithms to understand when, where and how its customers like to consume their products and determine the popularity of individual products based on location. Coca-Cola uses a number of emerging technologies, including Artificial Intelligence (AI), big data, cloud computing, blockchain technology, Internet of Things (IoT), robotics and behavioral analytics to achieve operational efficiencies and improve customer experience.

– BanQu Platform:

The Coca-Cola Company has engaged in several strategic partnerships and collaborations in the areas of technology, technology development and launches, acquisitions and technology investments over the past several years. For example, Coca-Cola partnered with BanQu to launch a blockchain-based platform to empower waste collectors and small sales centers across South Africa. BanQu's online supply chain tracking and automated payment system uses blockchain technology to track recycled materials throughout the supply chain, providing price transparency for buyers and sellers. This integrated solution also allows waste collectors to store their earnings in secure e-wallets or withdraw cash from automatic cash withdrawal machines.

Evaluation: The Manufacturing Intelligence subsystem implemented by The Coca-Cola Company combines multiple technologies, such as Proficy software, Artificial Intelligence (AI), and the BanQu blockchain platform, to monitor and improve operational efficiency across their supply chain. This innovation reflects Coca-Cola's commitment to using the latest technology to improve visibility, social responsibility and customer experience. So with all these initiatives, Coca-Cola succeeded in achieving better operational monitoring, increased production efficiency, and a positive contribution to corporate social responsibility.

⇒ Output Subsystem

• Quality Subsystem

Quality subsystems are organized parts or components in a quality management system that focus on certain aspects of controlling, guaranteeing and improving the quality of products or services. Its function is to be able to assess the quality of the typed material when it is converted into finished goods. TQM (Total Quality Management) is a system that is implemented in the long term and continuously to satisfy consumers by improving the quality of the company's products. TCCC applies 5S and Kaizen theories within their company. Quoted from Forbes, Kaizen is a practice of improving oneself with small, gradual actions which will then become a habit and can lead to success. Another key aspect of kaizen is that it is a process of continuous improvement and never ends.

This Kaizen theory argues that it is not that difficult to introduce something new into a company, the difficult part is how to maintain and maintain momentum once it is introduced. The message of the kaizen philosophy is that there should not be a single day in a company without some kind of

improvement in a process in the company. The application of the Kaizen philosophy at The Coca-Cola Company aims to create a work environment that continues to develop and continuously improve processes in order to improve product quality, operational efficiency and customer satisfaction. 5S is the name of a workplace organization method that uses a list of five Japanese words that all start with the letter S. This list explains how to organize a work space for efficiency and effectiveness by identifying and storing items in use, maintaining areas and belongings. , as well as maintaining the new order. The 5S process can increase work morale, create a positive impression on customers, and increase efficiency and orderliness. 5S consists of 5 steps, namely Seiri, Seiton, Seiso, Seiketsu, and Shitsuke

– Kaizen

Application of Kaizen at The Coca-Cola Company (TCCC):

- 1) Continuous Improvement: Encourage a company culture that promotes continuous improvement in every aspect of operations, from production processes to supply chain management.
- 2) All Employee Involvement: Involving all levels of employees, from management to operational workers, to participate in identifying problems, finding solutions, and implementing gradual improvements.
- 3) Process Innovation: Implementing new or more efficient practices in production, distribution, and product management to improve quality and efficiency.
- 4) Waste Management and Efficiency: Reduce waste, increase efficiency in resource use, and manage waste more effectively.
- 5) Education and Training: Provide training to employees to understand and apply the Kaizen concept, as well as develop the skills needed to improve processes and product quality.
- 6) Cross-Departmental Team Collaboration: Promote cooperation between different departments to solve problems and implement cross-functional improvements.

– 5S theory

Application of 5S at TCCC:

- 1) Seiri: TCCC Identify and remove unnecessary items from the work area such as damaged or unused items, to free up space and improve efficiency.
- 2) Seiton: TCCC establishes efficient storage methods, namely through the use of visual signs, clear labeling, and an organized system of shelving and cupboards for equipment and materials.
- 3) Seiso: TCCC implements regular cleaning practices to keep work areas clean, perhaps with a daily or weekly cleaning schedule.
- 4) Seiketsu: TCCC creates fixed procedures or guidelines to maintain consistency in implementing 5S principles in all work areas.
- 5) Shitsuke: TCCC encourages a sustainable work culture by involving all team members in maintaining and maintaining continuously improved working conditions.

TCCQS (The Coca Cola Quality System) is a quality management system from the Coca-Cola system. This system helps coordinate and guide company activities to ensure quality in everything the company does. TCCQS's focus is on customer and consumer satisfaction, while also providing a framework for safety and environmental responsibility, in line with Coca-Cola's vision as a responsible global citizen. Coca-Cola follows the third evolution of TCCQS offering the following improvements in managing quality and accelerating quality system implementation:

- 1) Simplified, well-organized, modular structure.
- 2) Conformity to externally recognized standards.
- 3) Providing utilization of external resources such as training and audits, while addressing the unique needs of the Coca-Cola system.

This evolution further enables improved quality performance and business excellence driven by:

- 1) Integrate and align business and quality objectives with metrics to monitor performance;
- 2) Demonstrate active involvement of top management in quality management in each business unit;
- 3) Integrate preventive measures as a management tool;
- 4) Incorporate stricter demands when planning new product/service introductions;
- 5) Incorporate Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points (HACCP) into Quality Management System Standards; And,
- 6) Define problem solving methodology and tools to drive continuous improvement.

Evaluation: The implementation of a quality subsystem at The Coca-Cola Company reflects the company's commitment to achieving operational excellence and customer satisfaction. Through Total Quality Management (TQM), Kaizen, 5S Theory, and TCCQS, Coca-Cola shows its readiness to continue adapting to environmental changes and market demands. Continuous evaluation and continuous improvement efforts are key to ensuring that these systems remain relevant and effective in achieving the company's desired quality and sustainability goals.

Conclusions and recommendations

The Information System itself has an understanding, namely that it is a process of collecting, processing, analyzing and disseminating information to achieve a certain goal by utilizing an organized and orderly combination of people, hardware, software and databases which are arranged in such a way as to be able to collect, change and disseminate information within a company or organization. There are fragments of information systems, one of which is a manufacturing information system which is also used by one of the multinational beverage manufacturing companies, namely The Coca Cola Company. Manufacturing information systems have their own meaning, namely a computer-based system that works together in connecting other functional information systems in order to help companies in solving problems related to product manufacturing based on input, process and output.

As a multinational beverage company that has been around for a long time and has many branches throughout the world, The Coca Cola Company also implements a manufacturing information system within the company with the aim of maintaining, improving and monitoring the supply chain process in the process of producing quality products for consumers. The application of The Coca Cola Company's information system includes combining various technologies such as professional software, artificial intelligence (AI), and the BanQu block chain platform. All of this is done to monitor and improve operational efficiency throughout their supply chain.

Suggestion

From all aspects, The Coca Cola Company has sufficiently met the requirements for a large multinational company that is well known by many levels of society from various countries. They pay close attention to every detail of the process from the supply chain, advertising, distribution channels, production process, packaging and recycling of remaining packaging to the application of AI to monitor target markets and consumers. Here, The Coca Cola Company has succeeded in implementing almost all information systems with evidence that the company can continue to grow rapidly from the past until now and become a market leader in the carbonated drinks market compared to other competitors.

Suggestions for the future that can be made are to continue to maintain the company ecosystem so that all implementation of internal information systems and manufacturing can continue to run in the form of maintaining operating systems and tools and always carrying out supervision in every production process, considering how many and complex the information and manufacturing systems are. run by The Coca Cola Company, it would be a waste if the company could not maintain the systems that have been formed perfectly.

The Coca-Cola Company's future business prospects

The Coca Cola Company has long been known as a company that produces the best beverage brands among the public and is recognized in many countries for the quality of the products it produces. Based on this success, we feel that The Coca Cola Company may have the opportunity to enter new markets such as starting to produce snacks. light weights that can be labeled with different brands but still be under the same company. Why does this company have prospects for the snack food business

due to its complete facilities and extensive experience in producing drinks for a very long time, coupled with the people's habit of always consuming products from The Coca Cola Company accompanied by snacks or snacks? new ideas to attract more profits and gain more consumer share in the food and soft drink market in the world.

By adding product lines to The Coca Cola Company in the form of snacks or snacks, it is hoped that the company can become a market leader in the soft drink food market which is known to many people at large, and will also receive special attention in the eyes of royal consumers from drink product lovers, especially Coca Cola, which is considered to want to get out of its comfort zone after years of being involved in the world of beverage making, which if seen from the positive side will have a good impact on the continuity of the company so that it is not inferior to soft drink companies which continue to come and have the latest innovations.

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